

Determination of Arsenic by Polarographic Method

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Polarographic determination of trace quantities of arsenic has been reported. Most satisfactory results are obtained when 1.0 *N* HCl is used as a supporting electrolyte. 1 ml of 0.002% gelatin per 50 ml of the system eliminates the maximum and ensures a smooth polarogram. The $E_{1/2}$ value for As(III) is -0.41 V and as low as 5.6 ppm of As(III) can be determined by this method. Pb, Cd, Sb and Cu interfere in the determination. The method can be applied to the determination of As(V) after its reduction to As(III).

THE widespread use of arsenic compounds in industry and the growing concern over arsenic toxicity and possible carcinogenicity have led to the development of sensitive methods for the determination of arsenic. The various methods have been reviewed by Talami and Feldman¹. The classical methods of arsenic determination have limited sensitivity and, therefore, the most prevalent methods used are electrochemical methods. Polarography and related techniques² have been considerably used for trace determination. In the present studies, DC polarographic estimation of arsenic at microgram level has been reported.

Experimental

The instrument used was a Toshniwal manual polarograph with a d.m.e. and SCE cell assembly. Two accumulators of 2 volts each in series were the source of DC supply. The instrument was calibrated before use with a standard Weston cell.

As(III) stock solution (0.05 *M*) was prepared by dissolving 6.5 g pure sodium arsenate (Riedel) in distilled water and making upto 100 ml. A working solution (0.005 *M*) (375 μ g As/ml) was prepared by diluting this stock solution. The solution is sufficiently stable and can be used over a considerable length of time. The solutions of hydrochloric, sulphuric, perchloric, nitric and phosphoric acids used were 2 *M*. A freshly prepared 0.002% gelatin solution was used as maxima suppressor. Other chemicals used were of AR grade.

In all the studies, the total volume of the solution was maintained at 50 ml. The observations were recorded at room temperature ($\sim 25^\circ$). The capillary characteristics were $m=3.028$ mg/sec, $t=2.24$ sec, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}=2.39$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6}.

General procedure: 1 ml As(III) solution containing 375 μ g was taken in a 50 ml volumetric flask. To it 25 ml 2 *M* HCl was added followed by 1 ml 0.002% gelatin solution. The volume was made upto mark with distilled water, the solution transferred to polarographic cell and nitrogen gas was

bubbled for 20 min to expel oxygen. The polarogram was recorded in the -0.1 to -1.0 V vs SCE range.

Results and Discussion

The polarographic behaviour of arsenic(III) has been reviewed by Arnold and Johnson³. Arsenic exhibits two waves in acidic medium corresponding to the following two reactions.

Different acids have been used earlier as supporting electrolytes³⁻⁷. Both the reduction processes give well defined diffusion currents and use can be made of them in the analysis of arsenic.

In the present work, the first reduction process has been studied in detail and used in the analysis. Different concentrations of HCl were tried as supporting electrolytes. Systems were prepared that had effective concentrations of HCl as 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 *N*. The polarograms were recorded and the $E_{1/2}$ and i_d values were determined. A single reduction wave with $E_{1/2}$ value of -0.42 V was obtained for As(III) when 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 1.5 and 2.0 *N* HCl was employed. This has been attributed to the process $\text{As}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{As}^0$. Two waves were observed for 0.5 and 1.0 *N* HCl corresponding to two reduction processes. The two $E_{1/2}$ values obtained were -0.41 and -0.92 V. The first value is more prominent and comparable to the one reported in literature^{4,8}. In our studies, the first $E_{1/2}$ value was always used for measurement of other parameters. It was found that for the same concentration of arsenic the diffusion current obtained in 1.0 *N* HCl was more than the same in 0.5 *N* HCl. 1.0 *N* HCl was, therefore, used as a supporting electrolyte.

Experiments with 1 *N* solution of H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 , HClO_4 or H_3PO_4 as supporting electrolyte were performed. Although the $E_{1/2}$ values in these acids are not much different from that obtained in

HCl, the i_d values were found to be smaller. The i_d value in HCl is 16.2 while in sulphuric, nitric and perchloric acids it is 11.5, 11.8 and 11.4, respectively. In case of phosphoric acid, no reduction wave is observed.

A polarographic maximum is observed when no maximum suppressor is added. This is at -0.68 V and is in agreement with the reported value⁸. The presence of 1 ml 0.002% gelatin solution per 50 ml of the system completely suppresses the maximum. At higher gelatin concentrations, distortions were observed in the polarograms and the limiting current was ill defined.

The lowest determinable limit of As(III) was found to be 5.6 ppm. Polarograms of systems containing As(III) less than 5.6 ppm were ill defined with no appreciable diffusion current. A linear calibration curve of i_d against concentration is obtained in the range of 5.6 to 56 ppm of As(III) when the measurements are made at -0.41 V. From ten different sets of observations, the relative standard deviation was found to be 0.3%.

Effect of diverse ions : Several other ions were examined for their effect on arsenic determination. It was found that Sn^{4+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Sb^{3+} and Cu^{2+} interfere at all concentrations. The tolerance limit of other ions is $\text{Al}^{3+}(1:0.3)$, $\text{Fe}^{3+}(1:0.3)$, $\text{Zn}^{2+}(1:1)$, $\text{Mg}^{2+}(1:1)$, $\text{Co}^{2+}(1:1.5)$ and $\text{Ag}^+(1:0.7)$ (values are M : As).

Determination of As(V) : Pentavalent species of arsenic is electrically inactive and cannot be directly determined. In most of the natural samples (water), arsenic is present in pentavalent state and reduction of arsenic is necessary to facilitate its determination.

The use of sodium bisulphite as a reducing agent for arsenic (V) has been reported⁸. In our work, reduction was brought about using the same reagent.

Reduction time of 30 min and use of 1 M bisulphite solution brings about nearly 95% reduction. A standard 0.05 M As(V) solution was prepared by dissolving a known weight of As_2O_5 in warm water and making upto 250 ml. Different volumes (10, 50 and 100 ml) of this solution were taken and As(V) was reduced to As(III). It was then determined by the above method. The results obtained are within $\pm 1.18\%$ of the expected value. A prolonged time of reduction or varying the bisulphite concentration does not show any improvement in the process of reduction.

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